

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

ASSOCIATION BETWEEN C-REACTIVE PROTEIN AND THE ETIOLOGY OF DELIRIUM IN HOSPITALIZED PATIENTS: A RETROSPECTIVE OBSERVATIONAL STUDY.

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ABSTRACT. **Introduction.** Delirium is a common neuropsychiatric complication in hospitalized patients, particularly older adults. Its onset is influenced by predisposing and precipitating factors and is associated with adverse outcomes, including increased length of stay and mortality. Inflammation is a proposed pathophysiological mechanism. **Objective.** To examine the relationship between C-reactive protein levels, the etiology of delirium, and their association with hospital length of stay and mortality. **Materials & Methods.** A retrospective observational study was conducted at Hospital Ángeles del Pedregal from January 2018 to December 2022. Cases were identified using the Confusion Assessment Method. Data, including demographics, clinical characteristics, admission reactant levels, and delirium triggers, were extracted from electronic medical records. Nonparametric tests were used for analysis. **Results.** A total of 59 patients diagnosed with delirium were included. The mean age was 72.56 ± 16.5 years. Hypoactive delirium was the most common subtype (62.7%). Infectious triggers were present in 55.9% of cases. Higher C-reactive protein levels were significantly associated with an infectious etiology ($p < .001$) but not with mortality or ICU admission. No significant associations were found between the reactant levels and either the length of stay or mortality. **Conclusions.** These findings suggest a relationship between systemic inflammation and delirium of infectious etiology. This may inform the development of tools for risk stratification. Etiology-specific interventions remain essential to improving clinical outcomes.

KEYWORDS. C-reactive Protein; Delirium; Confusional Assessment Methods; Hospitalized Patients; Inflammation Research Studies.

INTRODUCTION

Delirium is a neuropsychiatric syndrome frequently observed in hospitalized patients, particularly in the elderly population. It is characterized by an acute and fluctuating disturbance in attention and cognition and is associated with increased morbidity, prolonged hospital stays, and elevated mortality rates (Lipowski, 1987; Wilson et al., 2020). Despite its clinical significance, up to 60% of cases remain unrecognized, particularly the hypoactive subtype (Fong et al., 2015). The pathophysiology of delirium is multifactorial, with neuroinflammation emerging as a central mechanism (Ormseth et al., 2023; Shafi et al., 2017). Systemic inflammation, often marked by elevated levels of biomarkers such as C-reactive protein (CRP), can compromise the integrity of the blood-brain barrier, facilitating the entry of inflammatory mediators into the central nervous system and triggering neuronal dysfunction (Khan et al., 2011).

Other proposed mechanisms include neurotransmitter imbalances, particularly cholinergic deficiency and dopaminergic excess, oxidative stress, and disruptions of the circadian rhythm (Maldonado, 2017). Advanced age is a primary predisposing factor, as age-related changes decrease physiological resilience to stressors such as infections or metabolic disturbances.

The diagnosis of delirium, as defined by the *Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, Fifth Edition* (DSM-5), relies on identifying a disturbance in attention and awareness with an acute onset and fluctuating course (American Psychiatric Association [APA], 2013). Validated tools such as the *Confusion Assessment Method* (CAM) are widely used for bedside detection due to their high sensitivity and specificity (Iglesider et al., 2022). Effective management requires identifying and treating the underlying etiology. Given the proposed link between inflammation and delirium, this study was designed to investigate the role of CRP as a biomarker in relation to the specific causes of the syndrome.

OBJECTIVE

To examine the relationship between CRP levels, the etiology of delirium, and their association with hospital length of stay and mortality in hospitalized patients at the Hospital Ángeles del Pedregal (Mexico City, México).

MATERIALS & METHODS

STUDY DESIGN, SETTING & SAMPLE

A retrospective observational study was conducted at Hospital Ángeles del Pedregal, a tertiary care institution in Mexico City, México. The study spanned from January 2018 to December 2022. The study population consisted of patients aged 20 years and older diagnosed with delirium at admission or during hospitalization, confirmed using the CAM. Patients with a documented history of a major neurocognitive disorder or with incomplete electronic records for the study variables were excluded.

MEASUREMENT INSTRUMENTS

The diagnosis of delirium was based on the CAM (Inouye et al., 1990). CRP levels were measured using standard laboratory immunoturbidimetric assays. Delirium subtypes (hyperactive, hypoactive, mixed) were determined retrospectively from clinical notes based on DSM-5 descriptors (APA, 2013). Delirium etiologies were categorized as infectious, neurological, or metabolic based on a consensus review of clinical, laboratory, and imaging findings, aligned with the *International Classification of Diseases Eleventh Edition* codes (ICD-11; World Health Organization, 2021).

PROCEDURE

Patient data were extracted from the hospital's electronic health record system. Extracted variables included demographics, clinical characteristics, admission CRP levels, length of hospital stay, Intensive Care Unit (ICU) admission, and in-hospital mortality. All data were anonymized. Two independent researchers cross-validated the dataset to ensure accuracy.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

This study adhered to the *Declaration of Helsinki* and was approved by the *Institutional Ethics Committee of Hospital Ángeles del Pedregal* (HAP-1080). Written Informed consent was waived in accordance with *National Research Ethics Regulations for Retrospective Studies Using De-Identified Data* (Consejo de Salubridad General, 2014).

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

The normality of continuous variables was assessed using Kolmogorov–Smirnov and Shapiro–Wilk tests, which indicated a non-normal distribution ($p < .001$). Consequently, nonparametric methods were applied. The Mann–Whitney U test was used for two-group comparisons, and the Kruskal–Wallis test was used for comparisons across three or more groups. Associations between categorical variables were evaluated using Pearson's chi-square test. A two-tailed p -value $< .05$ was considered statistically significant. Statistical analysis was performed using **IBM SPSS Statistics Version 25 (IBM-Armonk, 2020)**.

RESULTS

SOCIODEMOGRAPHIC & CLINICAL CHARACTERISTICS

A total of 59 patients were included in the study. The mean age was 72.56 years ($SD = 16.5$), with 30 females (50.8%) and 29 males (49.2%). Hypoactive delirium was identified in 37 patients (62.7%), hyperactive in 20 (33.9%), and mixed in 2 (3.4%). Infectious causes were the most frequent etiology ($n = 33, 55.9\%$), with respiratory infections (27.1%) and urinary tract infections (20.3%) being the most common. Neurological etiologies were identified in 4 patients (6.8%), and the remaining 22 patients (37.3%) presented with metabolic disturbances. The mean CRP level at admission was 29.1 mg/dL ($SD = 37.2$). A significant association was found between infectious etiology and CRP levels ($\chi^2 = 51.34, p < .001$). Among patients with infectious delirium, 48.5% had CRP levels between 11 and 50 mg/dL, and 30.3% had levels between 51 and 100 mg/dL. In contrast, 75.0% of patients with neurological triggers and 81.8% with metabolic triggers had CRP values between 0 and 10 mg/dL. A total of 3 patients (5.1%) died during hospitalization. A Mann–Whitney U test showed no significant difference in CRP levels between survivors and non-survivors ($U = 44.500, p = .589$). No significant associations were observed between ICU admission and delirium etiology ($\chi^2 = 2.79, p = .19$) or between mortality and CRP levels, etiology, or length of hospitalization. Results are shown in **Table 1**.

TABLE 1. MAIN CHARACTERISTICS AND OUTCOMES.

Variable	Value
Age, M (SD)	72.6 (16.5)
Sex, n (%)	Female 30 (50.8), Male 29 (49.2)
Delirium subtype, n (%)	Hypoactive 37 (62.7), Hyperactive 20 (33.9), Mixed 2 (3.4)
Etiology, n (%)	Infectious 33 (55.9), Neurological 4 (6.8), Metabolic 22 (37.3)
CRP, M (SD)	29.1 (37.2)
Significant association	Infectious etiology \times CRP $\chi^2 = 51.34, p < .001$
Mortality, n (%)	3 (5.1), ns with CRP ($U = 44.50, p = .589$)

NOTE. CRP = C-REACTIVE PROTEIN; NS = NOT SIGNIFICANT.

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STRENGTHS & LIMITATIONS

This study's strengths include the use of a validated screening tool (CAM) and the categorization of delirium subtypes and etiologies. The application of nonparametric methods was appropriate for the data distribution. Limitations should be acknowledged. The modest sample size may have limited the ability to detect associations with low-frequency outcomes, such as mortality. The retrospective design carries inherent risks of selection bias and incomplete data. Furthermore, reliance on CRP as a single inflammatory marker does not capture the full complexity of the immune response.

DISCUSSION

This study examined the association between systemic inflammation, measured by CRP, and the etiology of delirium in hospitalized patients. The primary finding was that CRP levels were significantly higher in delirium cases of infectious origin compared to those triggered by neurological or metabolic causes. This differential inflammatory response supports the hypothesis that systemic inflammation plays a role in the pathophysiology of delirium. The results are consistent with studies indicating that peripheral inflammatory markers may reflect central neuroinflammatory processes contributing to cognitive dysfunction (Khan et al., 2011; Shafi et al., 2017). The lack of association between CRP and mortality in our sample may be attributable to a type II error due to the small sample size and low event rate. The predominance of hypoactive delirium aligns with previous literature, which identifies this subtype as the most common and often underrecognized (Gual et al., 2018). From a pathophysiological perspective, systemic infections can increase blood-brain barrier permeability and activate microglia, suggesting that CRP has clinical utility as a contextual biomarker in the etiologic evaluation of delirium. While not predictive of outcomes in isolation, elevated CRP may serve as an early indicator of a potential infectious etiology, supporting more targeted diagnostic workups to neuroinflammation (Maldonado, 2017). This mechanism may explain the elevated CRP levels observed in infectious delirium.

CONCLUSIONS

Delirium is a multifactorial syndrome in which inflammation is implicated in the etiology and modulation. This study found that patients with infectious causes of delirium had significantly higher CRP levels than those with non-infectious triggers. Although CRP did not predict mortality or ICU admission in this cohort, its measurement may aid in the etiologic stratification of delirium. Future research should investigate additional biomarkers and incorporate longitudinal designs to elucidate the prognostic relevance of inflammatory profiles.

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